

EBFMC25-OP-42 · Atypical ECG Finding in Kounis Syndrome: Coexistence of ST-Segment Elevation and De Winter T-Waves

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Kounis syndrome is a physiologically based mast cell activation syndrome in which acute coronary syndromes (ACS) occur following exposure to an allergen. There are 4 main variants of the syndrome.

Case Presentation: In our case, a 47-year-old male patient was admitted to the emergency department with chest pain that started after a bee sting.

Discussion: ECG performed at the time of admission revealed ST segment elevation in leads DI-aVL-V1 and V2, reciprocal ST segment depression in leads DII-DIII and aVF, and de Winter T waves in leads V3-V6. Angiography revealed LAD stenosis.

Conclusion: No similar ECG pattern was found in the literature.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Kounis syndrome, deWinter T waves, ST segment elevation, anaphylaxia

INTRODUCTION

Kounis syndrome is characterized by mast cell activation and the occurrence of acute coronary syndromes (ACS), such as coronary spasm, abrupt myocardial infarction, and stent thrombosis, in response to allergen exposure (Kounis, 2016). In addition to being insufficiently recognized by clinicians, it is often difficult to diagnose. It should be considered in the differential diagnosis when cardiac symptoms occur following exposure to an allergen (Alblaihed & Huis In 't Veld, 2023). There are four main variants of the syndrome. Type 1 is associated with coronary vasospasm following allergen exposure in individuals with no underlying coronary artery disease. Type 2 is characterized by plaque erosion following allergen exposure in individuals with coronary atherosclerosis. Type 3 is associated with stent thrombosis after allergen exposure, while Type

4 is characterized by coronary artery bypass graft (CABG) thrombosis (Brancaccio et al., 2024). Treatment should target both the allergic component and the immune reactions that result in coronary vasospasm, thrombus formation, or plaque rupture. Treating the allergic reaction may relieve pain, but if cardiac ischemia is present, ACS guidelines should be followed (Alblaihed & Huis In 't Veld, 2023; Douedi et al., 2023). In this case report, we present a case of Kounis syndrome which developed after a bee sting and resulted in chest pain that led to a visit to the emergency department and the patient's atypical ECG pattern.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 47-year-old male presented to the ED with complaints of pressing, widespread chest pain, nausea, and vomiting following approximately 8–10 bee stings. The patient reported no history of chronic illness or medication use. His vital signs included a blood pressure of 140/80 mmHg, body temperature of 36.6°C, heart rate of 117 beats/min, respiratory rate of 16 breaths/min, and oxygen saturation of 99% on room air. Physical examination revealed one bee sting on the neck and 7-8 stings on the hand and arm, as well as edematous, hyperemic, blanching areas when pressure was applied. No uvular edema, rales, rhonchi, or dyspnea were seen. Electrocardiogram (ECG) taken upon admission showed ST-segment elevation in leads DI-aVL-V₁ and V₂, reciprocal ST-segment depression in leads DII-DIII and aVF, and upward-sloping ST-segment depression in leads V₃-V₆, followed by long, symmetrical T (Figure 1).

The patient was diagnosed with Kounis syndrome, and treatment for the allergic reaction was initiated with 120 mg (2 mg/kg) of intravenous (IV) methylprednisolone, 40 mg IV pantoprazole, and hydration with normal saline. Additionally, according to the ACS treatment protocol, 300 mg of oral acetylsalicylic acid and 6000 anti-Xa IU/0.6 mL of subcutaneous enoxaparin sodium were administered. Following treatment, the patient's symptoms regressed, and a follow-up ECG showed ST-segment depression in DII and aVF, as well as a QS segment with minimal ST-segment elevation in leads V1-V2, with the disappearance of the other findings (Figure 2).

Figure 2

Follow-up ECG after antihistamine and steroid treatment

ST-segment depression in DII and aVF, as well as a QS segment with minimal ST-segment elevation in leads V1-V2

The patient was consulted with the cardiology department and underwent coronary angiography. Angiography revealed a 60-70% narrowing with plaque and a partially resolved thrombus in the distal left anterior descending (LAD) artery (Figure 3).

Figure 3

Percutaneous coronary angiography image

Red arrow: Thrombus at the ostium of D1

Blue arrow: 60-70% stenosis in the proximal LAD at D1

A 3.0x20 mm stent was implanted in the LAD at 18 atm. Laboratory tests revealed a leukocyte count of $18.03 \times 10^3/uL$, C-reactive protein of 12.49 mg/L, and hemoglobin level of 16.9 g/dL. Liver and kidney function tests were within normal limits. The initial troponin-I level at presentation was 0.118 ng/mL (normal <0.3 ng/mL), and the control troponin-I level was 0.948 ng/mL. After coronary angiography, the patient was admitted to the coronary intensive care unit and was discharged with dual antiplatelet therapy following a 5-day follow-up. Consent was not deemed necessary since no personal data other than the patient's age and gender was shared.

DISCUSSION

Due to LAD artery obstruction, De Winter syndrome is an acute coronary syndrome that is similar to ST-segment elevation syndrome but does not exhibit a noticeable ST-segment elevation (Yan et al., 2020). There is still much to learn about the syndrome's pathogenesis. According to a suspected mechanism, the infarct area is too big and can only be captured with an aVR (Verouden et al., 2009). The gold standard for diagnosing De Winter syndrome is electrocardiography; features include long, pointed T waves, upsloping ST-segment depression at the J point, no ST-segment elevation in leads V1–V6, and relatively small ST-segment elevation in lead aVR (de Winter et al., 2008).

Kounis syndrome can be defined as an ACS resulting from an allergic, anaphylactoid, or hypersensitivity reaction caused by mast cell activation (Kounis, 2006). First described in 1991 by N.G. Kounis and G.M. Zavras as “allergic angina syndrome,” (Kounis & Zavras, 1991) case reports of acute myocardial infarction following penicillin allergy have been documented in the literature as far back as the 1950s (Pfister & Plice, 1950). Kounis syndrome is divided into four different types depending on the condition of the coronary arteries. Type I variant, which is the most common, is characterized by coronary spasm occurring in normal arteries, usually presenting with normal or elevated cardiac enzyme levels, and can lead to acute myocardial infarction. In Type II variant, coronary artery spasm occurs due to the release of inflammatory mediators, manifesting as ACS with plaque erosion or rupture (Fourie, 2016). In cases of stent thrombosis following drug-eluting stent implantation after 2009, eosinophils and mast cells found in the thrombus material suggested a hypersensitivity reaction, which has been classified as the Type III variant of Kounis syndrome (Chen et al., 2009). Type IV variant is characterized by CABG thrombosis following allergen exposure (Brancaccio et al., 2024). Although measuring histamine levels within the first 8 minutes after acute pain is recommended as a diagnostic tool, this is not feasible in the ED setting. Instead, serum tryptase levels can be measured every 30 minutes over a two-hour period (Kounis et al., 2019). Nonspecific ECG findings include ST-segment depression, atrial fibrillation, bigeminal rhythm, QRS widening, QT prolongation, ventricular ectopic beats, T wave inversion or flattening, sinus tachycardia, atrioventricular block, sinoatrial block, and ventricular fibrillation (Kounis, 2016). A literature review revealed a case report of Kounis syndrome coexisting with De Winter ECG patterns (Dai et al., 2021). In the presented case, both ST-segment elevation and De Winter waves were present in the precordial leads, which has not been previously reported in the literature. Additionally, the changes in the ECG pattern following treatment were noteworthy. In this case, the presence of plaque during angiography led to the classification of the patient as having the Type II variant. Diagnosing Kounis syndrome requires recognizing the simultaneous occurrence of an allergic reaction and ACS. In emergency situations, distinguishing this syndrome from classic acute myocardial infarction is critical, as the treatment approach may differ. For instance, treating the allergic component is important and typically requires antihistamines and corticosteroids, in addition to following standard ACS management protocols (Balta et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in addition to life-threatening events such as anaphylaxis and anaphylactic shock following allergic reactions, including animal stings, clinicians must be vigilant for Kounis syndrome, which can cause coronary vasospasm and be fatal. Increasing knowledge and skill levels regarding this syndrome is essential.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

- Alblaihed, L., & Huis In 't Veld, M. A. (2023). Allergic acute coronary syndrome–Kounis syndrome. *Immunology and Allergy Clinics of North America*, 43(3), 503–512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iac.2022.10.010>
- Balta, A., Ceasovschi, A., Şorodoc, V., Dimitriadis, K., Güzel, S., Lionte, C., ... & Şorodoc, L. (2022). Broad electrocardiogram syndromes spectrum: From common emergencies to particular electrical heart disorders. *Journal of Personalized Medicine*, 12(11), 1754.

- Brancaccio, R., Bonzano, L., Coconcelli, A., Boyko, R., Ienopoli, G., & Motolese, A. (2024). Recurrent Kounis syndrome: A case report and literature review. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*, 13(6), 1647. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm13061647>
- Chen, J. P., Hou, D., Pendyala, L., Goudevenos, J. A., & Kounis, N. G. (2009). Drug-eluting stent thrombosis: The Kounis hypersensitivity-associated acute coronary syndrome revisited. *JACC: Cardiovascular Interventions*, 2(7), 583–593. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcin.2009.04.017>
- Dai, W., Jiang, Z., & Zhong, G. (2021). De Winter sign associated with rose-induced anaphylactic shock: A new electrocardiographic manifestation of Kounis syndrome. *Journal of Xiangya Medicine*, 6.
- de Winter, R. J., Verouden, N. J., Wellens, H. J., Wilde, A. A., & Interventional Cardiology Group of the Academic Medical Center. (2008). A new ECG sign of proximal LAD occlusion. *The New England Journal of Medicine*, 359(19), 2071–2073. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMc0804737>
- Douedi, S., Odak, M., Mararenko, A., Ross, J., & Sealove, B. (2023). Kounis syndrome: A review of an uncommon cause of acute coronary syndrome. *Cardiology in Review*, 31(4), 230–232. <https://doi.org/10.1097/CRD.0000000000000436>
- Fourie, P. (2016). Kounis syndrome: A narrative review. *Southern African Journal of Anaesthesia and Analgesia*, 22(2), 72–80.
- Kounis, N. G. (2006). Kounis syndrome (allergic angina and allergic myocardial infarction): A natural paradigm? *International Journal of Cardiology*, 110(1), 7–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2005.08.007>
- Kounis, N. G. (2016). Kounis syndrome: An update on epidemiology, pathogenesis, diagnosis and therapeutic management. *Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine*, 54(10), 1545–1559. <https://doi.org/10.1515/cclm-2016-0010>
- Kounis, N. G., & Zavras, G. M. (1991). Histamine-induced coronary artery spasm: The concept of allergic angina. *The British Journal of Clinical Practice*, 45(2), 121–128.
- Kounis, N. G., Koniari, I., Velissaris, D., Tzani, G., & Hahalis, G. (2019). Kounis syndrome—not a single-organ arterial disorder but a multisystem and multidisciplinary disease. *Balkan Medical Journal*, 36(4), 212–221. <https://doi.org/10.4274/balkanmedj.galenos.2019.2019.5.62>
- Pfister, C. W., & Plice, S. G. (1950). Acute myocardial infarction during a prolonged allergic reaction to penicillin. *American Heart Journal*, 40(6), 945–947. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-8703\(50\)90191-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0002-8703(50)90191-8)
- Verouden, N. J., Koch, K. T., Peters, R. J., Henriques, J. P., Baan, J., van der Schaaf, R. J., ... & de Winter, R. J. (2009). Persistent precordial “hyperacute” T-waves signify proximal left anterior descending artery occlusion. *Heart*, 95(20), 1701–1706. <https://doi.org/10.1136/hrt.2009.174557>
- Yan, J., Wang, Q., Zhang, Z., Shi, G., Hua, J., Ying, R., ... & Zhu, J. (2020). De Winter syndrome as an emergency electrocardiogram sign of ST-elevation myocardial infarction: A case report. *ESC Heart Failure*, 7(6), 4353–4356. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ehf2.13008>

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